

DIELECTRIC CONSTANT AND DIPOLE MOMENT OF SOME DRUGS. PART II

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Dielectric constant of sulphanilamide has been determined in dioxane and the dipole moment calculated by applying the new equation. The moments of compounds related to sulphanilamide have been recalculated from the literature data and the moments discussed in the light of their structure.

The study of the dielectric properties of the sulfa drugs is very interesting from the point of view of their pharmacological properties. Unfortunately these drugs have been found to be high melting and insoluble in organic solvents. The dielectric constant of sulphanilamide, which is soluble in dioxane, has been investigated and the dipole moment calculated by applying the new equation of Jatkar *et. al.* (*J. Ind. Inst. Sci.*, 1946, 28A, Part II). The previous data on the dipole moment of sulphanilamide and related compounds have been also recalculated. The results are given in the following table.

TABLE I

w_g	$d.$	$P_2.$	$\mu \times 10^{18}.$	$\mu_D.$
1. Benzene sulphonamide Solvent=dioxane at 25°. $P_2 = 156.$				
0.004210	2.2987	1.028	3393	4.17
0.008237	2.2386	1.0287	3426	4.19
0.012069	2.4694	1.0295	3452	4.20
0.015631	2.5460	1.0311	3422	4.19
2. <i>p</i> -Phenylbenzene sulphonamide: Solvent=dioxane at 25°. $P_2 = 262.$				
0.004831	2.2834	1.0280	3746	4.32
0.008125	2.3338	1.0287	3717	4.30
0.011312	2.3835	1.0295	3717	4.30
0.016929	2.4697	1.0311	3689	4.28
3. Sulphanilamide Solvent=dioxane at 25°. $P_2 = 180.$				
0.004368	2.3496	1.0284	5556	5.37
0.007848	2.4635	1.0296	5552	5.37
0.010880	2.5629	1.0305	5557	5.38
0.017019	2.7681	1.0327	5620	5.40
* { 0.009798	2.9189	1.0331	5575	5.40
{ ,, (40°)	2.8292	1.0157	5062.5	5.35
4. (<i>p</i> -Aminophenyl) benzene sulphanilamide Solvent=dioxane at 25°. $P_2 = 230.$				
0.002465	2.2692	1.0276	6130	5.59
0.003828	2.3020	1.0281	6124	5.59
0.006156	2.3597	1.0284	6137	5.59
0.007888	2.4037	1.0291	6175	5.61

1-4 Kumler, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 63, 2182.

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DISCUSSION

Kumler *et al.* (*loc. cit.*) have calculated the moment of sulphanilamide by making use of the formula for free rotation,

$$\mu_{tr} = \sqrt{\mu_1^2 + \mu_2^2 + 2\mu_1\mu_2 \cos \theta \cos C_1 \cos C_2} \quad \dots (1)$$

where μ_1 is the moment of amine group, μ_2 , the moment of sulphonamide group, θ , the angle between the axis of rotation, and C_1 and C_2 , the angles which the two moments make with their respective axis of rotation. The calculated moment by applying this formula is 5.82 which is less than the observed Debye's value of moment 6.63, and hence he postulated about 3% contribution of the resonance structure

According to Kumler the therapeutic effects of sulphanilamide and related compounds are associated with the contribution made by the forms with a separation of charges. The recalculated values of moments are 4.19 for benzene sulphonamide ($C_6H_5SO_2NH_2$) and 1.5 for aniline and 5.4 for sulphanilamide ($H_2NC_6H_4SO_2NH_2$), which is 0.3 less than the sum of aniline and sulphonamide. Similarly, the recalculated moment 5.6 of the compound *p*-phenylbenzene sulphanilamide

is 0.2 less than the sum of the moments of the corresponding *p*-phenylbenzene sulphonamide

(4.3D) and aniline. These differences are considerably less than the discrepancies (0.8) given by the equation (1) and also those calculated by the addition of the D.C.M. moments of aniline (1.9) and benzene sulphonamide (5.1) the sum of which is more than the D.C.M. moment 6.6 for sulphanilamide which result cannot be explained by the concept of resonance.

The application of the new equation clears away the whole difficulty and the observed moment is nearly equal to the sum of the individual moments.

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